

Analysis of Deixis Types in Joko Widodo's Speech: A Pragmatic Linguistics Study

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study, "Analysis of Deixis Types in Joko Widodo's Speech: A Pragmatic Linguistics Study," is to identify and classify the many types of deixis used in Joko Widodo's speeches. Personal deixis, temporal deixis, spatial deixis, discourse deixis, and social deixis are five different categories of deixis that are identified. The study uses a pragmatic linguistic framework and a descriptive analytic methodology. The information for the study was taken from transcripts of speech given by Joko Widodo performed at the Sentul International Convention Centre in Bogor, West Java. The analysis demonstrates that the use of deixis in Joko Widodo's speeches contributes significantly to rhetorical efficacy, political discourse building, and communication techniques. The study's conclusions can be applied to language instruction, communication training, and giving public speakers advice on how to use deixis effectively. Future research directions can look at differences in deixis usage in various circumstances or comparison analysis with other political speeches.

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, there was a discipline exploring the relationship between the external environment and the meaning of speech based on situation or context. It was called as pragmatics. For instance, learning pragmatics was an essential issue. The teaching and understanding of pragmatics would help native and non-native speakers overcome the challenges of international communication (Lin, 2007). In order to increase a better communication, it is essential to analyze a part of pragmatics called deixis. Deixis, pointing, is the use of general terms in order to refer to specific person, place, time, social status, or discourse based on context. This research aimed to analyze deixis because of several reasons.

The first reason, as it is the part of pragmatics, deixis has essential role in understanding language based on context. To support this argument, deixis is the most noticeable technique in manifesting relationship between language and context (Khalili, 2017). In addition, learning deixis can ease people in understanding language (Sasmita et al., 2018). It means that understanding deixis helps people denote the words or phrases that have contextual information. Contextual information, in this case, refers to person, place, time, social status, or discourse. The text without contextual information or background context is not an informative text.

People should understand the contextual information of deixis in order to understand communicative language because deixis has fluctuative references (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021). It means that understanding contextual information will help people to understand the contextual meaning of words because every word has its own contextual information. For example, the sentence "I am here" was understood when the addressee understand the context of "I" and "here". These words have more than one references based on speaker and the situation used in communication. The word "I" can be referred as Budi if the speaker was Budi, but it can be Wati if the speaker was Wati. The word "here" refers to beach if the communication happens in the beach, but it can be a "house" if the communication occurs in the house.

Despite deixis' importance in communication, little research has specifically examined the varieties of deixis used in speeches by Indonesian President Joko Widodo. Although there are numerous research on deixis, there hasn't been a thorough examination of the different deixis kinds used in Joko Widodo's speeches. Understanding the various deixis types he uses in his speeches can help us gain important understanding of his rhetorical style, political philosophy, and communication tactics. The enquiry into the deixis types used by Joko Widodo, their purposes, and their implications for political communication will be guided by this research question. This study intends to clarify the linguistic and pragmatic features of Joko Widodo's communication style by identifying and analysing the many deixis types that are used in political speeches.

The second reason, Deixis makes meaning of language becomes more organized and effective, so it doesn't cause a confusion and a different perception (Purwandari et al., 2019). The presence of deixis in a text will reduce

word repetition so that language use becomes more efficient and effective. For example, the word "my book" in a sentence can be replaced by the word "it", so the word "my book" will not be repeated again in the next sentence. In light of this, a fascinating research challenge is presented by the examination of the deixis types used in Joko Widodo's speeches. We may learn more about how he uses deixis to improve the organisation and efficacy of his communication by examining the individual deixis kinds used in his talks. The techniques he uses to preserve coherence, prevent misunderstanding, and encourage a clear grasp of his intended message can be revealed through this research. Deixis patterns in his speeches can also provide important details about his communication style and the ways in which he adapts his language to successfully engage and connect with his audience. The following formulation of the research problem is possible:

1. What specific deixis types are used in Joko Widodo's speeches?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Type of Deixis

Deixis is divided into five different forms according to Levinson (1983), each of which can be used as a linguistic tool to communicate precisely. Person deixis is the first, and it uses words that refer to specific people or groups to influence how discourse interacts with others. The second sort of deixis uses locatives like "here" and "there" to indicate place and anchors language in spatial situations. The third category, time deixis, makes use of temporal cues like "now" and "then," enabling speakers to move across temporal planes of speech. The fourth sort of deixis, social deixis, establishes social roles and relationships by using words like "you," "we," and honorifics. The fifth form, discourse deixis, uses words like "this," "that," and "these" to organize speech and lead listeners through the story.

METHODS

This study used a descriptive analysis approach, which is a type of qualitative research strategy. The objective was to present a thorough analysis of the deixis types used in Joko Widodo's speech, taking into account both their pragmatic and functional ramifications. The study used a qualitative method in order to capture the complexity and subtleties of deixis usage and to provide a thorough analysis of the contextual elements affecting its application. The remarks Joko Widodo made while serving as president of Indonesia served as the source of the data for this study.

The site (<https://www.thejakartapost.com/news/2019/07/15/we-can-be-one-of-strongest-countries-in-the-world-jokowis-full-speech.html>), which was accessed by the researcher on January 3, 2020, served as the data source for this study. The speech in question was given by President Joko Widodo to his supporters at the Sentul International Convention Centre in Bogor, West Java, as his first speech following his reelection. This speech served as the primary source of information for the study's deixis analysis and provided insightful

information about the pragmatic and functional aspects of deixis usage in relation to Jokowi's discourse. When it came to recording the remarks made by Joko Widodo while he was president, these sources were regarded as trustworthy and authoritative. Specifically created for this project, a systematic coding scheme served as the main tool for data gathering. A variety of deixis categories, including personal deixis (pronouns, names), spatial deixis (demonstratives, locatives), and temporal deixis (time expressions, adverbs), among others, were intended to be identified and categorised by the coding scheme. This tool made sure that deixis types were consistently and reliably identified and examined across the corpus of speech.

The process of gathering data included a thorough review of the chosen speech. Each utterance was carefully scrutinised, and deixis occurrences were found and recorded in accordance with the predetermined coding method. The speaker's aims, the audience, and the sociopolitical setting in which the speech was made were all taken into consideration by the researcher while analysing each deixis usage. To ensure complete coverage of deixis types in Joko Widodo's speech, the data gathering method was carried out in an organised and iterative manner.

The deixis types that were discovered underwent a qualitative analysis as part of the data analysis. Based on the many Deixis categories, the coded data were arranged and categorised. Deixis usage patterns and trends were discovered, and their purposes and practical ramifications were examined. The investigation focused on how deixis influenced Joko Widodo's communication methods. The results were evaluated and discussed in the context of pertinent pragmatic and linguistic theories.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

As was said in the introduction, the main goal of this study was to investigate the particular varieties of deixis that Jokowi uses in his speech. In order to achieve this goal, the researcher carried out a thorough examination and came up with five unique deixis categories: person, time, location, discourse, and social deixis. The combination of these categories offers a thorough framework for comprehending how Jokowi uses deixis as a language device for efficient communication. The detected deixis categories were compiled in a tabular fashion in order to show the results in a structured manner. The resulting Table offers a clear visualisation of each deixis type's relative relevance inside Jokowi's talks by showing not only the frequency of each type but also the associated percentages.

Table 1. Percentage of Types of Deixis

No.	Type of Deixis	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Person	88	62,8%
2.	Time	8	5,7%
3	Place	9	6,5%
4	Discourse	27	19,3%
5	Social	8	5,7%

Total	140	100%
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Adapted from (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021)

The analysis shows the distribution of deixis types in Jokowi's speeches based on the data in Table 1's data. Notably, person deixis (participant) accounts for the biggest share (62.8%), followed by temporal deixis (time), spatial deixis (place), social deixis (society), and discourse deixis (text), all of which account for 5.7%, 6.5%, 5.7%, and 19.3%, respectively. These percentages highlight the importance of person deixis, which is used 88 times throughout Jokowi's speech. The researcher also provided a thorough and in-depth assessment of the deixis usage patterns in the context of Jokowi's speeches in the discussion that followed each single datum.

Table 2. Person Deixis

No.	Person Deixis	Frequency	Percentage
1.	I	18	20,4%
2.	We	44	50%
3.	Them	3	3,4%
4.	Our	7	8%
5.	They	1	1,1%
6.	It	6	6,9%
7.	You	3	3,4%
8.	Us	2	2,3%
9.	Their	1	1,1%
10.	Me	1	1,1%
11.	Myself	2	2,3%
Total		88	100%

Adapted from (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021)

The first type of deixis found in the Jokowi's speech was person deixis. Based on Table 2, there were 11 words recognized as person deixis that were "I", "we", "them", "our", "they", "it", "you", "us", "their", "me", and "myself". Specifically, the deixis "I" appeared 18 times in total i.e. 20,4%, "we" appeared 44 times (50%), "them" appeared 3 times (3,4%), "our" occurred 7 times (8%), "they" appeared once (1,1%), "it" appeared 6 times (6,9%), "you" appeared 3 times (3,4%), "us" appeared twice (2,3%), "their" appeared once (1,1%), "me" appeared once (1,1%), and "myself" occurred twice (2,3%). Based on the frequency and percentage, the word "we" was the most person deixis used in the Jokowi's speech. This thorough analysis of person deixis usage sheds light on Jokowi's linguistic approach and demonstrates his skill at adapting his speech to successfully engage with different people or groups. He personalizes his discourse and creates relationships with his varied audience by using distinct person deixis, which eventually increases the effect of his message.

Table 3. Time Deixis

No.	Time Deixis	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Now	2	25%
2.	Right now	1	12,5%
3.	First	1	12,5%
4.	Secondly	1	12,5%
5.	Third	1	12,5%
6.	Fourth	1	12,5%
7.	Fifth	1	12,5%
Total		8	100%

Adapted from (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021)

The second type of deixis used in the Jokowi's speech was time deixis or temporal deixis. There were 7 words that were classified as time deixis. These words were "now", "right now", "first", "secondly", "third", "fourth", and "fifth". Viewed from table 3, the percentages of every time deixis used in Jokowi's speech were 2 (25%) for "now", 1 (12,5%) for "right now", 1 (12,5%) for "first", 1 (12,5%) for "secondly", 1 (12,5%) for "third", 1 (12,5%) for "fourth", and 1 (12,5%) for "fifth". It means that the word now was the most time deixis used in the Jokowi's speech. This distribution emphasises how carefully he used these temporal markers to organise his argument and direct the audience's understanding of time. Interestingly, "now" appears more frequently in speech than other time deixis, indicating its importance in Jokowi's speech. This demonstrates how Jokowi uses precise time deixis to support his arguments and emphasise the temporal component of his message. In addition to offering insights into Jokowi's speechcraft, the examination of these time deixis highlights the rigorous planning that went into his use of deixis for effective communication.

Table 4. Place Deixis

No.	Place Deixis	Frequency	Percentage
1.	There	6	66,7%
2.	Where	3	33,3%
Total		9	100%

Adapted from (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021)

In Jokowi's speech, the third type of deixis was place deixis or spatial deixis. There were two types of place deixis called as "there" and "where". There were two words of place deixis called as "there" and "where". The word "where" appeared six times (66,7%). In the other hands, the word "there" appeared 3 times (33,3%). It can be stated that "there" was the most place deixis used in Jokowi's speech. Evidently, the word "where" appears a lot in Jokowi's speech, emphasizing its importance and indicating a purposeful use to ground his narrative in different spatial locations. We may learn more about how Jokowi uses these language strategies to make his points clear and help his

audience better understand the spatial aspects that are inherent in his communications by looking at the distribution and frequency of these place deixis.

Table 5. Social Deixis

No.	Social Deixis	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Bapak	1	12,5%
2.	Ibu	1	12,5%
3.	Ladies	2	25%
4.	Gentlemen	2	25%
5.	Brother	1	12,5%
6.	Sister	1	12,5%
Total		8	100%

Adapted from (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021)

The fourth type of deixis used in the Jokowi's speech was social deixis. In data analysis, the researcher found six words recognized as social deixis. These words were "bapak", "ibu", "ladies", "gentlemen", "brother", and "sister". Based on table 5, the word "bapak" appeared once, "ibu" appeared once, "ladies" appeared twice, "gentlemen" appeared twice, "brother" appeared once, and "sister" appeared once. It means that the word "ladies" and "gentlemen" were the dominant social deixis used in the Jokowi's speech. Notably, Jokowi strategically uses the terms "ladies" and "gentlemen" to engage and address his audience, emerging as the dominating social deixis inside his talks. Examining the prevalence of these social deixis allows us to understand how Jokowi plans to foster a welcoming and personalized discourse environment. These linguistic decisions not only highlight his capacity to build rapport, but also highlight his efforts to modify his language in order to connect with various audiences efficiently.

Table 6. Discourse Deixis

No.	Discourse Deixis	Frequency	Percentage
1.	That	19	70,4%
2.	These	1	3,7%
3.	This	5	18,5%
4.	Which	2	7,4%
Total		27	100%

Adapted from (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021)

The last type of deixis used in the Jokowi's speech was discourse deixis. There were four words categorized as discourse deixis namely "that", "these", "this", and "which". The word "that" was used 19 times (70,4 of deixis used in the Jokowi's speech was discourse deixis. There were four words categorized as discourse deixis namely "that", "these", "this", and "which". The word "that" was used 19 times (70,4%), the word "these" was used once, the word "this"

was used 5 times, and the word “which” was used twice. As a result, the word “that” was the most discourse deixis used in the Jokowi’s speech. The thoughtful placement of these discourse deixis emphasises Jokowi's effort to precisely direct the listener through his speech. By using these phrases, he not only conveys clarity and consistency but also makes it easier for the audience to grasp how his story is connected to other stories. This research sheds light on Jokowi's planned use of deixis and careful consideration of language structure to increase the overall impact of his remarks.

Person Deixis

Person deixis is the grammatical categories related to person covering pronouns (speaker, hearer, or addressee) that are relevant to the text or discourse (Levinson in Hidayati et al., 2022). Similar to previous study written by (Hidayati et al., 2022) person deixis was the dominant type of deixis used as it appeared mostly in the text. This type of deixis can be called as personal deixis as it focuses on the participant’s role in the sentence. In addition, It can be identified as the personal pronouns in the part of speech that have a function as subject, direct object, indirect object, object of preposition and complement in the sentence. It means that it is used to replace people, thing, places, animal, ideas, and so fourth in order to make the sentence more understandable and brief. As it is relevant to personal pronoun, person deixis can be divided into three types covering first person (I, me, we, us, and so fourth), second person (you, your, yours, and so fourth), and third person (he, she, it, they, and so fourth). Data below were the discussion about findings related to words identified as person deixis.

Datum 1

“We know the characteristics of this global.....”

The underlined word “we” was a kind of person deixis as it was a pronoun replacing plural first person. In this context, the word “we” refers to speakers and the audiences of the speech. This word can also refer to the Indonesian as the speech context is about nasional speech involving Indonesian.

Datum 2

“...The moment I see something that is”

In this sentence, there was a word categorized as a person deixis. This word was “I”. This word was recognized as a person deixis because of its role. Its role is to replace the singular first person. It was directly spoken by the speaker himself. It means that the word “I” in this context refers to the speaker. The speaker of this speech was Joko Widodo.

Datum 3

“.....I will check and I will beat [them] up....”.

In the next datum, there was underlined word categorized as a person deixis. This word was “them”. It can be called as a person deixis as it replaced some parties (people) in sentence. It can also be called as plural third person pointing the objects of sentence. It was the pointing of the phrase “illegal levies” because of the context used in the speech of Joko Widodo.

Datum 4

“Our demographics are also very strong.....”

In the datum 4, there was a person deixis namely “our”. This word was the person deixis categorized as possessive personal as it represented the ownership or belonging. It was the plural possessive pronoun as it shows the ownership of the speaker and the audiences of Joko Widodo’s speech.

Datum 5

“.....they can contribute to Indonesia's development”

The word “they” in the above sentence was a kind of person deixis as it points to some parties. This person deixis can be categorized as plural third person. It was called as third person because it refers to some people excluding the speaker and the audiences of the speech.

Time Deixis

Temporal deixis, also known as time deixis, is the process of encoding temporal time points and distances dependent on the speaker's context (Wicaksono in Febriza, 2020). In addition, this deictic expression is a general term that refers to specific time as the setting of sentences. It concerns on the moment of utterance or the time when the text was spoken or written. It means that this kind of deixis focuses on time adverbs or temporal adverbs answering “when”. In learning tenses, we can find this type of deixis as the time signals. In addition, temporal deixis replaces words describing when the action happened or occurred. Viewed from data analysis, there were some words indicated as temporal deixis. These deictic expressions were described in the discussion below.

Datum 6

“.....now we live in a very dynamic global environment.....”

From datum 6, we can see a deictic word classified as time deixis. It was the word “now”. It was a temporal deixis as it focused on specific time. Viewed from its grammatical function, this deictic word was a kind of adverb of time. To support this statement, Adverb of time can be categorized as temporal deixis (Pratiwi & Utomo, 2021). In addition, this word refers to the time when the speech was spoken.

Datum 7

“.....First, we will continue the development of”

From the sentence above, there was an underlined word called as temporal deixis. This word was “first”. It was identified as a deictic word as it had relation to certain time. It means that this word expressed time adverbs and certain time events. Viewed from the context used, the term “first” denotes the start of a series of events.

Place Deixis

In pragmatics place deixis can be called as spatial deixis. This deictic expression focuses on pointing location expression related to the speaker (Natalia & Santoso, 2020). Lyons (2010) defines place or spatial deixis as the specification of position in relation to obtaining points in speech occurrences (Natalia & Santoso, 2020). It can be defined as a type of space deixis dealing with locations. It means that spatial deixis refers to the setting of the utterance

specifically the place where the communication happens. in this part, there were two words of place deixis that were described below.

Datum 8

“There cannot be an increase in stunting, maternal mortality.....”

In the datum 8, There was a deictic word classified as place deixis. This term was "there." This word encodes the place where the utterance was spoken. This word can be classified as a local deixis as it relates to the place. Viewed from its grammatical role, this word was a demonstrative adverb. It is a distal deixis, alluding to something far away from the speaker.

Social Deixis

Social deixis is a kind of deixis that refers to social relationship and social distinction showing the social relationship between speakers and (listeners, audiences, or addressee) (Anggara, 2017). It also focuses on the social characteristics. Based on those statements, social deixis does not concerns on three main deixis components called as person, time, and place. Social deictic words demonstrate how different social rankings and communication participants use language to express relationships within society.

Datum 9

“Ladies and gentlemen of the audience....”

From the datum 9, there were two underlined words known as social deictic words, as these words express the social class of people. These words were "ladies" and "gentlemen". They refer to the audience. These deictic expressions were in the plural form. It means that they refer to groups of people. The words "ladies" and "gentlemen" were used in order to talk to audiences in a polite way. The word "ladies" was for women, but the word "gentlemen" was for men. Those terms were used to show the audience's social traits in an old-fashioned way, or to emphasize the audience's high social class.

Discourse Deixis

Similar to social deixis, it does not deal with three main parts of deictic words namely person, time, and place. The usage of some phrases with some utterances to refer to some portions of the unfolding discourse in which the utterance (including the text referencing expression) is positioned is referred to as discourse deixis (Levinson in Anggara, 2017). This discourse deixis is useful for referring to certain parts of a conversation. The demonstrative that and this are two deictic terms that are employed in conversation deixis.

Datum 10

“We have work toward a country that is more productive, that is competitive, that is highly flexible in facing changes.....”

In datum 10, there was an underlined word indicated as the text deixis. This term was "that." This word was repeated three times, but it referred to the same reference. It was used to refer to portions of the discourse that included the speech, including the utterance itself. It refers to the word "country". It was a kind of relative pronoun that conjoined some sentences into a complex sentence.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, Joko Widodo uses a variety of deixis techniques in his speech, including person deixis, time deixis, place deixis, discourse deixis, and social deixis. These results shed important light on the linguistic and pragmatic techniques Joko Widodo used to communicate as the president of Indonesia. The analysis showed that Joko Widodo regularly employed person deixis, such as pronouns and names, to create a sense of inclusivity and shared identity. In order to place events and emphasise temporal features, time deixis, including time expressions and adverbs, were used. This technique was successful in communicating a sense of urgency or historical relevance. Place deixis, like demonstratives and locatives, were used to highlight particular locales and build spatial allusions, increasing audience engagement and comprehension. Furthermore, the employment of deixis markers that regulated speech and promoted coherent conversation allowed for the observation of discourse deixis. Finally, Joko Widodo's use of honorifics and titles to address dignitaries, emphasising respect and authority, played a critical part in building social interactions and power dynamics.

Suggestion

The data indicate various research suggestions. First, political speech deixis can be studied for their rhetorical impact and persuasive methods. This would help us understand how deixis improves political communication. Comparative studies can also examine deixis use in political speeches from different eras. This would illuminate how deixis shapes political speech and how it may vary between settings and individuals. This study also improves language and communication training. Language learners can improve their pragmatic skills by learning how to strategically use deixis in talks. This study improves our understanding of deixis in political speeches and has consequences for linguistics, political communication, language education, and public speaking.

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